

DELIVERABLE D3.3

GUIDELINES FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF REFERENCE VALUES

WP3 – Quality Assessment for Omics Technologies

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable we report on efforts of EATRIS-Plus sites in the certification of pre-analytical sample processing and in the development of reference values and material for omics technologies used to generate the multiomics data in WP1.

The technical validity of an experimental process, the quality of the resulting data and reproducibility of the results can be assessed by comparing the data to a known range of values that were developed from well-characterized samples and controlled experimental conditions. Since the experimental processes can differ widely, it is useful to develop target ranges of detection, that are applicable to most commonly used technologies. The development of reference material and the use of target value ranges is discussed in principle and in examples.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this part of EATRIS-Plus is to collect information on the establishment of reference samples and material, being an integral part of quality control processes. Although the goal of EATRIS-Plus is not the development of reference values or material, EATRIS-Plus members have been strongly involved in the co-development of such tools in international consortia. Other EATRIS-Plus members have set up certification processes for quality control of pre-analytical processes, so-called proficiency testing. Here we report on the individual efforts, in particular in the technology areas which are employed in the efforts of WP1, where a multiomics dataset with omics technologies is generated.

DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

BACKGROUND

The use of standards in the scientific community offers the potential for comparability, reproducibility and consistency of data. Hence, standards ultimately contribute to the more effective reuse of data and option of data integration. In the realm of software analysis tools, standardized formatting of data input is required in some instances and is indispensable for sharing results and interpretation of data. In the laboratory, reference materials can be used to develop benchmarks, and protocols for the assessment of quality. The application of these standards can be used to compare the performance of analytical and technological platforms or workflows, prior to their deployment to research, industry or the clinic. The choice of the reference material largely depends on the intent of use (IoU). Some of the IoUs are training, method validation, measurement uncertainty, and calibration, as well as external quality assessment, such as proficiency testing. Depending on the IoU, different types of reference material are required. Some commonly encountered types of reference materials are as follows: 1. **Pure substances** characterised for chemical purity and/or trace impurities; 2. **Standard solutions and gas mixtures**, often prepared gravimetrically from pure substances and used for calibration purposes; 3. **Matrix reference materials**, characterised for the composition of specified major, minor or trace chemical constituents. Such materials may be prepared from matrices containing the components of interest, or by preparing synthetic mixtures; 4. **Physico-chemical**

reference materials characterised for properties such as melting point, viscosity, and optical density; **5. Reference objects or artefacts** characterised for functional properties such as taste, odour, octane number, flash point and hardness. This type also includes microscopy specimens characterised for properties ranging from fibre type to microbiological specimens.

Certified material would be used for example for method validation, but for in-house quality control the level of certification for a reference material could be relaxed. However, homogeneity and stability are essential parameters at any rate. Value assignment of proficiency testing samples through reference value calibration of the certified reference material value is an expensive and time-consuming process, which sometimes can be replaced or accompanied by consensus value determination by expert laboratories.

The successful application of reference material in combination with a valid method depends on its correct use, both with regard to operator skill and suitability of equipment, reagents and standards. It is highly recommended that the work is carried out by experienced staff, applying validated methods, using validated equipment, under conditions which allow the comparison with historical data or other laboratories, and can be tested via third-party performance measurements such as proficiency testing. Reference material is produced by internationally renowned institutions such as NIST, government-sponsored programmes, commercial groups and academic sites. The level of certification is dependent of the supplier, and it is the user's responsibility to use the material accordingly.

In the clinical setting, the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of patients depend on accurate laboratory data. Therefore, a reference measurement must be established to ensure the validity of clinical data. Reference measurements will ensure the precision and accuracy of the laboratory tests providing metrological traceability to the clinical analysis. In order to achieve this, a system must be in place which includes the definition of the measurand, the measurement procedures, reference material, and the target range or value.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

Since EATRIS-Plus project is not equipped to establish either reference material or reference values, we provide here some examples of the work and contributions of EATRIS-Plus sites, which had been aimed towards that goal.

EXAMPLE 1:

Proficiency Testing programme

Quality control (QC) checks are essential for evaluating the reliability of data produced by a laboratory and for producing technically defensible data. Many quality control checks are done internally, such as the use of method blanks, matrix spikes, and laboratory control samples. A good quality assurance program will periodically utilize an independent third-party to evaluate the proficiency of its laboratory through participation in Proficiency Testing (PT) or Performance Evaluation (PE) studies.

Proficiency Testing and Performance Evaluation studies are both independent objective studies used to evaluate the quality of data produced by a laboratory through analysis of blind samples provided by an outside source:

- 1 An outside source (or provider) provides a sample to the laboratory in which the sample composition is unknown to the laboratory
- 2 The laboratory analyzes the sample as part of its normal testing procedure or Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)
- 3 The results from the lab is sent back to the provider who evaluates the results using statistical methods
- 4 The provider then sends the laboratory (and accrediting authorities) the evaluation that includes the performance index or score, upon which the laboratory's accreditation is partly dependent.
- 5 Based on the result of the test, the laboratory will evaluate its performance, which may include any necessary implementation and corrective actions.

Periodic participation in PT/PE studies should be a natural part of a laboratory's routine check of quality control measures. Regular participation in PT/PE studies can help:

- 1 Identify deficiencies early and demonstrates a good quality assurance program which is important for the maintenance of laboratory accreditation.
- 2 Positive evaluations by reputable PT/PE studies validate the technical competency of a laboratory. This provides data end-users with confidence in the data's accuracy.
- 3 Comparative information about method and instrument performance
- 4 Overview of the quality of specific analyses in a sector, country or region

Biospecimen Proficiency Testing (PT), as defined in ISO/IEC 17043:2010 (the International Standard on "Conformity assessment –General requirements for proficiency testing"), is seen as a powerful tool to help laboratories demonstrate their competence and efficiency in biospecimen processing and characterisation to researchers, industry, and accreditation bodies. In the context of the EATRIS-Plus project, the project partners will participate in the PT with the aim to ensure the fitness-for-purpose of samples for downstream omics analyses. The results of the quality assessment will allow to conclude on minimal performance quality metrics required. As only the Processing schemes are applicable in WP3.2.1 of the EATRIS-Plus project, the description of the testing schemes will not be addressed hereafter.

The PT Programme belongs to the category of inter-laboratory comparison Schemes involving simultaneous participation of Laboratories in different countries in the world. In the processing schemes, randomly selected aliquots from a source material prepared at IBBL (the Processing Items) are distributed simultaneously to Participants for concurrent processing. The Participants' processed "output materials" (e.g. DNA, RNA) are sent back to IBBL for isochronous testing. The results are used to assess Participants' processing efficiency.

In each programme, participants receive after registration **standardized samples produced and shipped by IBBL** to the participants' premises. Participants use their routine processing methods to extract the samples. For production of Processing items, the following aspects are important:

- **Fitness-for-purpose:** the processing items must be compatible with all processing methods which may be used by participants (eg. Whole blood stabilizer, compatible with all DNA extraction methods)
- **Homogeneity:** the aliquots must be sufficiently homogenous. For this reason, continuous homogenization of liquids during the aliquoting is critical.
- **Stability:** the processing item must be stable under the shipment conditions (temperature) and between the time of production and the time of processing by the participants.

Preparation of any Processing Item also includes aliquoting and labelling. At least 10 “processing” runs (e.g. 10 extractions from 10 Processing Items, selected randomly across the range of aliquots) are performed, followed by measurements. Finally, the mean and standard deviation (SD) are calculated. The uncertainty linked to processing is also calculated. Stability studies do not have to be repeated for every batch of material produced: once stability conclusions have been reached, they apply to any material of the same type, produced with the same methods. Processing Items are prepared and packed according to the IATA regulations and, depending on the conditioning of the samples to be shipped, the schemes are shipped at either Room Temperature or Dry Ice.

The received processing items are then processed by the participants using their standard routine method. Participants capture general **pre-analytical data** on the PT online platform, which contains Scheme-specific data entry questionnaires. Reported data include, for eg., reception date of the samples, extraction information such as equipment, method and kit used, elution buffer and volume...

Once all processed samples have been returned to IBBL by the participants, IBBL proceeds with **isochronous testing, statistical analysis** and **benchmarking**: the information in the online questionnaire is exported by IBBL, normalized against the data from the results of the isochronous testing of the extracted derivatives and then imported in a software to conduct statistical analysis. A statistical design is decided in advance to meet the objectives of a specific Scheme, based on the nature of the data (quantitative vs qualitative), the statistical assumptions, the sources of uncertainty and the expected number of results.

Statistical procedures used are those proposed by the International Harmonised Protocol for the Proficiency Testing of Analytical Chemistry Laboratories (IUPAC technical Report 2006). All results provided by Participants will be analysed with the same statistical method and individual results are assessed against an assigned value. For quantitative results such as RNA Yield, the mean, median, standard deviation and range are provided (see Figure 1 below). For qualitative results, such as level of PCR Inhibitors (SPUD assay), the modes (most common responses) and range (lowest and highest response) are provided (see Figure 2 below). In both cases, graphs are produced with the results from all Participants. For processing schemes, the **Assigned Values** are the **average obtained by all the Participants**, while the **standard deviation is the standard deviation of all the Participants**. Results are analysed globally (all extraction methods) and also by individual method. The scoring system is based on distance from the Assigned Value. For most parameters measured, the scoring system used assigns “Very Satisfactory” and “Satisfactory” scores when deviation from assigned value is less or equal to 2 standard deviations, “Questionable” score when is greater than 2 standard deviations and “Requiring Action” score when is greater than 3 standard deviations. An external experienced group of professionals with relevant technical knowledge and experience will review in details all the results falling into the “Questionable” and “Requiring Action” performance outcome, to

provide additional advice to Participants. At the end of each programme, IBBL sends to each participant a personalized report, a certificate and a label of participation.

Figure 1
 Scheme RNA Extraction from Frozen Tissue: Extracted Frozen Tissue RNA Yield per mg Tissue

Figure 2
 Scheme DNA Extraction from Frozen Tissue: Level of PCR Inhibitors (SPUD Assay)

EXAMPLE 2 :

Fudan Quartet Samples as reference material for multiomics quality assessment

The EATRIS-Plus Work Package 3 deals with the data quality generated by the EATRIS-Plus sites which also contribute to the multiomics dataset in work package 1 (DNaseq, mRNAseq, microRNAseq, methylSeq, metabolomics, proteomics, and microRNA-Q-RT PCR). After some deliberations towards the identification of suitable reference material for internal quality control and possible alignment of experimental processes and data quality across EATRIS-Plus sites in the different omics platforms used work package 1, we learned about the newly established multiomics reference material at the Fudan University in Shanghai, China. The Fudan team employed the widely used protocol using Epstein-Barr

virus (EBV) to establish immortalized lymphoblastoid cell lines (LCLs) from the Quartet family members including father (F7), mother (M8), and two monozygotic twin daughters (D5 and D6) who were enrolled in the Fudan Taizhou cohort. DNA, RNA, proteins, and metabolites were isolated concurrently from the same set of four LCLs for the preparation of multi-omics reference materials in large quantities (>16,000 vials in total) (**Figure 3**). Huge amounts of data for each of the four omics types (genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics) were generated in triplicates in different laboratories in terms of intra-batch, inter-batch, cross-lab, and cross-method comparisons, resulting in over 100 TB multi-omics data. Together, the reference material is termed the Quartet Samples. Over the recent years, the Fudan team was able to generate large amounts of the Quartet samples consisting of DNA, RNA, proteins or metabolites, suitable for the intent of use of this task of work package 3. The Quartet samples contain a natural qualitative built-in genetic truth, and quantitative biological multi-omics differences among Quartet family members enabled the Fudan team to develop quality control metrics to (1) objectively evaluate the intra-batch performance for each type of omics data, (2) monitor and correct batch effects in large samples studies, and (3), offers the use as a model system for quality control of multi-omics integration algorithms. Aliquots of the Quartet samples are shipped to EATRIS-Plus and tested at different sites. The data will then either be analysed within the EATRIS-Plus Digital Research Environments, or uploaded to the Fudan Data Portal, which generates quality assessment reports. The reports and the results of the internal comparative analysis can be used to align the experimental procedures when differences in quality of the data are observed.

Figure 3

Fudan Quartet Sample generation. The Quartet EBV transfected lymphoblastoid cell lines (LCLs) were obtained from four donors from Fudan Taizhou Cohort, including Father (F7), Mother (M8), and two monozygotic twin daughters (D5 and D6). Multiomics reference materials (DNA, RNA, protein, and metabolite) were constructed from the same batch of cell expansion, and aliquoted into more than 1000 tubes for each individual at each omic level for communitywide uses.

One of the most well-known and best-characterized set of samples in the field of genomics developed by the “Genome-in-a-bottle” (GIAB)-consortium, a NIST project (<https://www.nist.gov/programs->

[projects/genome-bottle](#)). The goal of GIAB, a public-private-academic consortium is to develop the technical infrastructure (reference standards, reference methods, and reference data) to enable translation of whole human genome sequencing to clinical practice and innovations in technologies. The priority of GIAB is authoritative characterization of human genomes for use in benchmarking, including analytical validation and technology development, optimization, and demonstration. A number of samples and pilot genomes have been put in place for the public to sequence, such as pilot genome (NA12878/HG001) from the [HapMap project](#), and two son/father/mother trios of Ashkenazi Jewish and Han Chinese ancestry from the [Personal Genome Project](#).

For clinical sequencing purposes, such as those aimed at identifying mutations in tumor, it would be most useful to establish reference material, benchmarking data and workflows which address more than just the reliability of sequencing technology, but also the determination of such mutations as benchmarks of the entire process. Since the GIAB sample set only constitute DNA from normal tissue, a different approach for clinical, in particular cancer sequencing needed to be established. The US-FDA driven community effort SEQC2 began their efforts in 2015, and set on to sequence and analyse immortalized cell line samples from human tumors in combination with cell lines from matched normal cell lines. The samples were sequenced with different technology platforms in several laboratories, and analysed by many data science teams across the globe. Several EATRIS (including EATRIS-Plus) sites participated in this effort, and the results were published in 2020 and 2021 in peer-reviewed journals Nature Biotechnology, Genome Biology and Scientific Data.

For the purpose of this deliverable we describe and summarize some of the results with immediate relevance to this deliverable in the light of the technologies we use in WP1 of EATRIS-Plus and WP3. Since several EATRIS sites provided sequencing data, analysed the data bioinformatically and participated in the manuscript writing, and thus are data owners, we take the freedom of copying some parts of the publications into the sections, always with proper citation.

EXAMPLE 2: SEQC/SEQC2

The following introduction to the SEQC2 is based on Mercer et al (2021), which was authored on behalf of the SEQC consortium, to which several EATRIS sites are partners (1). The MicroArray and Sequencing Quality Control (MAQC) consortium is a FDA-led, community-wide effort to evaluate the use of genomic technologies in clinical applications (2). This evaluation includes the benchmarking of NGS technologies, the development of reference materials, and understanding the experimental and bioinformatic variables that impact the accuracy and reproducibility of large genomic datasets. These outcomes are ultimately used to inform best-practice guidelines, regulatory considerations, and foster further improvements in genomic technologies and computational methods (3). The MAQC consortium has been ongoing for almost 16 years with four projects (MAQC I-IV). The founding project, MAQC Phase I, was initiated in 2005 by the FDA's National Center for Toxicological Research (NCTR) to evaluate the reliability of microarray technologies that were being increasingly used in research, clinical diagnosis, and drug development and thus posed an urgency for the FDA to address the regulatory implication of the technology (4, 5). In 2010, the MAQC consortium launched the SEQC (Sequencing Quality Control, known as MAQC III) project to investigate emerging next-generation

sequencing (NGS) technologies. This SEQC project established best-practice use of RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) for measuring gene expression, compared RNA-seq performance to microarrays (6), evaluated the inter-platform reproducibility of NGS technologies (7), and evaluated the bioinformatic tools increasingly required to analyze large and complex RNA-seq data-sets (8).

The SEQC2 project, in which several EATRIS-Plus and EATRIS sites participated, had three specific aims: (i) develop reference materials that could be shared by laboratories for standardized evaluation of NGS technologies, (ii) benchmark the impact of experimental and bioinformatic variables on the generation and analysis of NGS data and, (iii) evaluate inter- and intra-lab reproducibility of NGS technologies across different laboratories [8]. The SEQC2 project is organized into six themes, each focusing on a different clinical application, including genome sequencing, cancer genomics, single-cell sequencing, circulating tumor DNA, epigenetics (eDNA methylation), and targeted RNA sequencing (see Fig. 4). Together, the diverse research and clinical laboratories that participated in the SEQC2 evaluated the performance of these differing NGS applications and built consensus standards for their best-practice use in clinical settings.

Figure 4

Schematic overview of the MAQC/SEQC2 project organization, aims and methods used for analytical validation of NGS technologies. (1)

The main SEQC2 outcomes are reference materials and reference datasets which can be applied to evaluate a broad range of NGS technologies of today and tomorrow to establish best practice and support regulatory framework development. NGS is being increasingly adopted for the clinical diagnosis of disease and drug development, and it is critical for the research and clinical community to understand sensitivity, accuracy, and reproducibility of NGS in routine application. Over the past 10 years, the SEQC and SEQC2 projects undertaken by the MAQC consortium have performed analytical validation of NGS technologies across a diverse international network of research and clinical laboratories to support this real-world adoption.

The ambition of the SEQC2 project is to support the translation of emerging NGS technologies into routine clinical practice. This includes the analyses of pre-analytical variables, such as sample type,

preparation, and input amount, as well as post-analytical variables, such as the impact of different bioinformatic tools on the interpretation of complex NGS datasets. These pre- and post-analytical variables are often overlooked during proof-of-principle demonstrations by test developers, but markedly impact test performance.

The SEQC2 project has also established reference materials that are commercially available as an ongoing resource for the research and clinical community. These materials enable scientists to establish and benchmark their NGS workflow, compare performance with consortium data [10, 15], and guide efforts by related scientific communities, such as the Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities (ABRF). Similarly, the large number of datasets and protocols generated during SEQC2 are available as an accessible resource for ongoing development of bioinformatic tools [12]. However, despite these resources, final clinical validation of NGS assays using patient samples is required prior to clinical use. The SEQC2 project has highlighted the variables that impact the accuracy and reliability of NGS across a range of applications. We anticipate these findings will inform the interpretation and analysis of genome data in regulatory practice. Previous findings from MAQC have been incorporated into draft FDA guidance for pharmacogenomics and in vitro diagnostics, as well as the use of genetic variant databases to support germline disease diagnosis [18, 19]. This has contributed to a regulatory understanding of genomic data that is now routinely submitted as part of medical product applications, with drug approvals increasingly incorporating genotypes in indications on product labels.

More broadly, the success of the SEQC2 also reflects the continued efforts of an enduring international collaboration of scientists from different backgrounds in academia, industry, and government that together form the MAQC consortium. The project has proven a template for community-wide and open-science efforts seeking to understand the performance of NGS technologies across diverse clinical and research laboratory contexts. Together these scientists aim to support the translation of rapidly evolving NGS technologies that will ultimately increase our understanding of disease, improve the diagnosis and care of patients, and benefit human health.

EXAMPLE 2.1 Whole genome sequencing and Whole exome sequencing

The following paragraphs in this example are taken from Zhao et al. (2021) (9), which was co-authored by EATRIS members.

With the rapid advancement of sequencing technologies, next generation sequencing (NGS) analysis has been widely applied in cancer genomics research. More recently, NGS has been adopted in clinical oncology to advance personalized medicine. Clinical applications of precision oncology require accurate tests that can distinguish tumor-specific mutations from artifacts introduced during NGS processes or data analysis. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop best practices in cancer mutation detection using NGS and the need for standard reference data sets for systematically measuring accuracy and reproducibility across platforms and methods. Within the SEQC2 consortium context, we established paired tumor-normal reference samples and generated whole-genome (WGS) and whole-exome sequencing (WES) data using sixteen library protocols, seven sequencing platforms at six different centers. We systematically interrogated somatic mutations in the reference samples to identify factors affecting detection reproducibility and accuracy in cancer genomes. These large

cross-platform/site WGS and WES datasets using well-characterized reference samples will represent a powerful resource for benchmarking NGS technologies, bioinformatics pipelines, and for the cancer genomics studies.

The overall study design is shown in **Figure 5**. Briefly, DNA was extracted from fresh cells or cell pellets mimicking the formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) process with fixation time of 1, 2, 6, or 24 hours. A small amount of DNA from fresh cells of HCC1395 and HCC1395BL was pooled at various ratios (3:1, 1:1, 1:4, 1:9 and 1:19) to create mixtures. Both fresh DNA and FFPE DNA were profiled on NGS or microarray platforms following manufacturer recommended protocols. To assess the reproducibility of WGS and WES, six sequencing centers performed a total of 12 replicates (3 x 3 + 3) on each platform. In addition, 12 WGS libraries constructed using three different library preparation protocols (TruSeq PCR-free, TruSeq-Nano, and Nextera Flex) in four different quantities of DNA inputs (1, 10, 100, and 250 ng) were sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq 4000, and nine WGS libraries constructed using the TruSeq PCR-free protocol were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq. Finally, Affymetrix Cytoscan HD and single-cell sequencing with 10X Genomics platform were performed to uncover the cytogenetics and heterogeneity of two cell lines.

We first established reference call sets with evidence from 21 replicates of Illumina WGS runs with coverage ranging from 50X to 100X (1150X in total). We split mutation call confidence levels into four categories: HighConf, MedConf, LowConf, and Unclassified. By combining all WGS runs, we were able to further confirm and improve our call set with tumor-normal pairs of 1500X data sets and identified mutations with VAF as low as 1.5%. A subset of reference mutation calls was validated by targeted exome sequencing (WES at 2,500X coverage) using HiSeq, and deep sequencing from AmpliSeq (at 2,000X coverage) using Miseq, and Ion Torrent (at 34X coverage), and long-read WGS by PacBio Sequel (at 40X coverage). In addition, we inferred subclones and heterogeneity of HCC1395 with bulk DNA sequencing. The results were confirmed by single-cell DNA sequencing analysis.

The established call sets have at least two advantages over the others: (1) the whole genomes of reference samples were sequenced with deeper coverage at a total of 1,500X and were validated by orthogonal sequencing platforms; consequently, high-confidence clonal and subclonal somatic mutations were called and validated; and (2) somatic mutations called from 378 datasets (21 sequencing replicates by three aligners and by six somatic mutation callers) were consolidated by two state-of-the-art machine learning-based somatic mutation classifiers to construct a high-confidence somatic reference call set, which alleviated calling errors specific to sequencing platform, sequencing site or bioinformatics algorithm.

With defined reference call sets, we then systematically interrogated somatic mutations to identify factors affecting detection reproducibility and accuracy. By examining the interactions and effects of NGS platform, library preparation protocol, tumor content, read coverage, and bioinformatics process concomitantly, we observed that each component of the sequencing and analysis process can affect the final outcome. Overall WES and WGS results have high concordance and correlation. WES had a better coverage/cost ratio than WGS.

However, sequencing coverage of the WES target regions was not even. In addition, WES showed more batch effects/artifacts due to laboratory processing and thus had larger variation between runs, laboratories, and likely between researchers preparing the libraries. As a result, WES had much larger inter-center variation and was less reproducible than WGS. Biological (library) replicates removed some artifacts due to random events (“Non-Repeatable” calls) and offered much better calling precision than did a single test. Analytical repeats (two bioinformatics pipelines) also increased calling precision at the cost of increased false negatives. We found that biological replicates are more important than bioinformatics replicates in cases where high specificity and sensitivity are needed.

Reference sample	Sample type	Platform	Data set
 Normal cell line HCC1395BL	Fresh DNA	WGS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hi Seq • NovaSeq • PacBio • 10X Genomics WES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HiSeq • Ion Torrent • AmpliSeq • MiSeq Microarray <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affymetrix CytoScan 	Reproducibility: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intra-center WGS • Inter-center WGS • Cross-platform Library preparation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Library kit • DNA input amount Validation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confirmation • Specificity • Sensitivity
	FFPE DNA Mixture DNA	WGS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HiSeq WES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HiSeq 	FFPE process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fixing time: 1h, 2h, 6h, 24h • DNA damage Tumor purity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 75%, 50%, 20%, 10%, 5%
 Tumor cell line HCC1395	Fresh cells	scCNV <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10X Genomics 	Number of cells: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HCC1395BL: 983 • HCC1395: 1465

Figure 5

Study design for the experiment. DNA was extracted from either fresh cells or FFPE processed cells. Both fresh DNA and FFPE DNA were profiled on WGS and WES platforms for intra-center, inter-center and cross-platform reproducibility benchmarking. For fresh DNA, six centers performed WGS and WES in parallel following manufacture recommended protocols with limited deviation. Three library preparation protocols (TruSeq-Nano, Nextera Flex, and TruSeq PCR-free,) were used with four different quantities of DNA inputs (1, 10, 100, and 250 ng). DNA from HCC1395 and HCC1395BL was pooled at various ratios to create mixtures of 75%, 50%, 20%, 10%, and 5%. For FFPE samples, each fixation time point (1h, 2 h, 6 h, 24 h) had six blocks that were sequenced at two different centers. All libraries from these experiments were sequenced on the HiSeq series. In addition, nine libraries using the TruSeq PCR-free preparation were run on a NovaSeq for WGS analysis.

EXAMPLE 2.2 Germline variants

The following paragraphs in this example are taken from Fang et al. (2021) (10), which was co-authored by EATRIS members.

Accurate somatic mutation detection is essential for cancer genomics and precision cancer medicine. Despite rapid advances in sequencing technologies, it remains challenging to detect somatic mutations accurately using next-generation sequencing (NGS). It is difficult to obtain consistent and concordant somatic mutation calls from individual platforms or pipelines, hampering the development of personalized therapies. In addition, quality control of somatic mutation pipelines is often insufficient due to the lack of well-validated and publicly available reference samples and reference datasets. Therefore, paired tumor–normal reference samples with high-confidence somatic mutation calls are desirable and urgently needed (11). As more sequencing technologies and bioinformatics pipelines are used to identify clinically actionable somatic mutations, the need grows even stronger. The lack of samples for generating standardized DNA datasets for setting up a sequencing pipeline or benchmarking the performance of different algorithms limits the implementation and uptake of cancer genomics. Several EATRIS have participated in a community effort run by the US FDA, called SEQC2 (Sequencing Quality Control project phase 2) towards the description of reference call sets obtained from paired tumor–normal genomic DNA (gDNA) samples derived from a breast cancer cell

line—which is highly heterogeneous, with an aneuploid genome, and enriched in somatic alterations—and a matched lymphoblastoid cell line. We partially validated both somatic mutations and germline variants in these call sets via whole-exome sequencing (WES) with different sequencing platforms and targeted sequencing with >2,000-fold coverage, spanning 82% of genomic regions with high confidence (**Figure 6**). Although the gDNA reference samples are not representative of primary cancer cells from a clinical sample, when setting up a sequencing pipeline, they not only minimize potential biases from technologies, assays and informatics but also provide a unique resource for benchmarking ‘tumor-only’ or ‘matched tumor–normal’ analyses. To establish reference data and call sets for benchmarking somatic mutation calling, we extracted gDNA samples from a triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) cell line (HCC1395) and a B lymphocyte-derived normal cell line (HCC1395BL) from the same donor from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). Unlike reference call sets derived from CLL and MB tumors with low mutation burden and very limited structural changes, the HCC1395 cell line is rich in genomic alterations (~40,000 SNVs, ~2,000 small insertions and deletions (indels), CNAs in ~56% of the genome and >256 complex genomic rearrangements, an aneuploid genome and BRCAness) and has been characterized previously using cytogenetic analysis and array-based comparative genomic hybridization. Moreover, we preferred HCC1395 over a normal cell line with engineered mutations or synthetic DNA spike-in30 because it is difficult, if not impossible, to engineer a whole range of somatic mutations into host chromosomes to mimic the complexity and heterogeneity of a cancer genome.

Figure 6

Twenty-one sequencing replicates for the tumor (HCC1395) and normal (HCC1395BL) gDNA samples were performed at six sequencing centers. They were grouped into five groups shown as colored squares on the far left. The sequencing platforms used were HiSeq and NovaSeq, and the sequencing experiments were performed at Illumina (IL), Fudan University (FD), Novartis (NV), European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine (EA), National Cancer Institute (NC) and Loma Linda University (LL). Each of the 21 sequencing datasets was aligned with three aligners to create a total of 63 pairs of tumor–normal BAM files. For each of the 63 tumor–normal BAM files, we ran six somatic mutation callers (MuTect2, SomaticSniper, VarDict, MuSE, Strelka2 and TNScope) followed by SomaticSeq and NeuSomatic machine learning classifiers using models built specifically for these datasets. Initial tier was assigned to each variant call based on how consistently the variant was classified as a somatic mutation across different sequencing centers and aligners. Then, to rescue low-VAF variants into the reference call set, we ran the same variant-calling pipeline on two higher-depth datasets: an independent 350× replicate sequenced on a HiSeq at Genentech (GT) and a 400× replicate by combining nine NovaSeq replicates at Illumina (IL). High-confidence calls from those two datasets were

used to promote less-reproducible low-VAF variants from the 21 sequencing replicates into the reference call set. Then, we combined all of our short-read sequencing data into a pair of 1,500× tumor–normal and used it to rescue additional low-VAF variants into the reference call set. Finally, we cross-referenced our Illumina short-read-based high-confidence calls with PacBio long-read sequencing data and removed a small number of calls that were inconsistent with each other. The high-confidence calls (labeled PASS) were considered ‘true’ somatic mutations, and genomic regions with low-confidence calls were removed from the high-confidence regions. Chr, chromosome; Pos, position.

Our reference samples and their call sets can have broad applications in benchmarking sequencing pipelines. For example, we used the reference call sets to benchmark WGS and WES in companion studies (9, 12), which compared various experimental conditions to determine factors encompassing both analytical technology platforms and bioinformatic methods that affect the reproducibility and accuracy of somatic mutation detection. In particular, the variants in high-confidence regions can help to assess detection sensitivity and specificity. Our reference samples have also been used to benchmark single-cell RNA-sequencing technologies (13), and the associated data are available to the community (14). The characteristics of genetic alterations in HCC1395 cells are in line with what have been described in a large cohort study (15). The changes in ploidy observed in HCC1395 cells are common for breast cancers (16). Therefore, the large number of somatic mutations and CNAs in HCC1395 cells provides the genomic representativeness desired in a reference gDNA sample. In addition, many variants and mutations in HCC1395 cells have clinical implications. Genetic materials derived from the paired tumor–normal cell lines are sustainable for community usage. We chose cell lines over real tissues to extract gDNA as somatic reference samples because real tissues are not renewable. In this study, we made a large batch of gDNA from each of the two cell lines and distributed aliquots to the sequencing centers to develop reference call sets. The remaining gDNA can be used for validating or benchmarking any emerging sequencing technologies or protocols. Should the need for additional gDNA arise, cell aliquots derived from the same batch of the reserved master cells can be used for the production of gDNA, and genetic drift can be characterized with a bridging study using our gDNA materials and the reference call sets. We propose the call sets reported here as a reference and expect that the reference call sets and high-confidence regions might be further refined as sequencing technologies and data analysis tools improve.

EXAMPLE 2.3

Methylation Sequencing

The following paragraphs in this example are taken from Foox et al. (17), which was co-authored by EATRIS members.

DNA methylation plays a key role in the regulation of gene expression (18), disease onset (19), cellular development (18), age progression (20), and transposable element activity (21). Whole-genome bisulfite sequencing (WGBS) is increasingly used for fundamental and clinical research of CpG methylation. Numerous validated protocols and commercially available kits are available for WGBS library preparation (22–24). Other assays to interrogate the epigenome include oxidative bisulfite sequencing (25), and targeted approaches (26), further accelerating the breadth and rate of discovery in genome-wide DNA methylation studies. As the field of epigenomics continues to advance, there is a need to establish definitive standards and benchmarks representative of the methylome. In recent years, the Genome in a Bottle (GIAB) Consortium has established seven human cell lines as reference

material to enable genomics benchmarking and discovery (27). Recent studies have characterized the genomes of these cell lines (e.g., germline structural variant detection in (28)), but none yet have examined the epigenome. Here, the FDA's Epigenomics Quality Control (EpiQC) Group, which includes EATRIS-Plus and another EATRIS site, presents DNA methylation sequence data across all seven GIAB reference cell lines, as well as a comparative analysis of targeted and genome-wide methylation protocols, to serve as a comprehensive resource for epigenetics research. We build on top of work done in previous studies to compare the performance and biases of WGBS library kits (e.g., (23, 29, 30)) by evaluating both commonly used and newly available epigenomic library preparation kits. We report the relative performance of each kit, as measured by mapping efficiencies, CpG coverage, and methylation estimates. We then characterize the reproducibility and challenges of methylation estimation across the genome. We further sequenced these cell lines using long-read technology on an Oxford Nanopore PromethION and here compare its performance alongside more common chemical/enzymatic conversion kits and short-read sequencing. Finally, we generated microarray data for these cell lines and provide guidelines for normalization of beta values, site filtration, and comparison to sequence data. This reference dataset can act as a benchmarking resource and a reference point for future studies as epigenetics research becomes more widespread within the field of genomics.

We generated epigenomic data for seven well-characterized human cell lines (HG001-HG007) that have been designated as reference materials for genomic benchmarking by the Genome in a Bottle (GIAB) Consortium (27). These cell lines include NA12878 (HG001) from the CEPH Utah Reference Collection, as well as two family trios from the Personal Genome Project, one of Ashkenazi Jewish ancestry (HG002-4) and one of Han Chinese ancestry (HG005-7). Libraries for whole epigenome sequencing were prepared using a variety of common bisulfite and enzymatic conversion kits, including NEBNext Enzymatic Methyl-Seq (referred to here as EMSeq), Swift Bio sciences Accel-NGS Methyl-Seq (MethylSeq), SPLinted Ligation Adapter Tagging (SPLAT), NuGEN TrueMethyl oxBS-Seq (TrueMethyl), and Illumina TruSeq DNA Methylation (TruSeq). Cell line genomic DNA was acquired from Coriell, and one aliquot of each genome was extracted and distributed to six independent laboratories, each utilizing one library preparation method.

Each site prepared two technical replicates per cell line for their respective epigenetic assay. In the case of EMSeq, libraries were prepared at two sites, designated as Lab 1 and Lab 2. All other sites were designated as Lab 1 for their library type. In the case of TrueMethyl, pairs of replicates were made using a bisulfite-only treatment (BS) and an oxidative bisulfite treatment (OX). All libraries were pooled into equimolar concentrations and sequenced in multiplex at one site, resulting in a range of 500 M to 3.5B paired-end reads per replicate. The range of sequencing depth per replicate resulted from an imbalance in library pooling, as well as differences in shearing condition and size selection per library type. In addition to short-read sequencing of epigenetic libraries, Oxford Nanopore R9.4.1 PromethION flow cells (referred to here as Nanopore) were run to generate long read sequence data for each genome, each ranging from 75B to 250B bases.

The EpiQC study provides a comprehensive epigenetic benchmarking resource using human cell lines established by the Genome in a Bottle Consortium as reference materials to advance genomics research. We provide datasets for a broad range of methylome sequencing assays, including short-read whole-genome bisulfite sequencing (WGBS) and enzymatic deamination (EMSeq), and native 5-methylcytosine calling using Oxford Nanopore long-read sequencing. We also provided data from targeted approaches, including reduced representation bisulfite sequencing (Methyl Capture EPIC), methylated DNA immunoprecipitation and sequencing (MeDIP-seq) for mC and hmC, and the Illumina Infinium MethylationEPIC 850k array. While most of the published and/or commercialized assays have been tested with some standard samples (e.g., GM12878), the sample used to benchmark each assay was drawn from different DNA aliquots, extracted from cells grown at different passages, and potentially grown in different media. Here, aliquots of the same gDNA were distributed across multiple laboratories and used for all data generated. To remove additional variability, all libraries were

sequenced on multiple flow cells of one Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (then a third flow cell on the same instrument type). For all assays, libraries were produced in duplicates, providing both inter- and intra-assay datasets.

Benchmarking whole methylome sequencing technologies is important for determining which method will achieve the best performance, and to provide recommendations and standards for experimental design within future studies. Large projects such as the NIH Roadmap Epigenomics Project (31), the International Human Epigenome Consortium (32), and the Cancer Genome Atlas (33) have produced, compiled, and analyzed a vast amount of WGBS data comprising tissues and cell lines from normal and neoplastic tissues. Building upon these previous works, our study encompasses an up-to-date range of commonly used whole methylome assays as well as emerging methods such as enzymatic methylation and native 5mC calling from long-read technologies and provides data across 7 different reference material cell lines, providing a comprehensive examination of DNA methylation analysis methods. We found that the library preparation method of choice and parameters used within each protocol can significantly impact data quality and utility for biological interpretations. Libraries with longer inserts benefited from less adapter contamination, fewer dovetailing (overlapping) reads, and fewer low-quality bases, which increased mapping efficiency and mean coverage per CpG. This is particularly impactful when one chooses to employ a cost-effective sequencing on an Illumina system with paired-end 150 bp reads, as was done within this study. This sequencing scheme resulted in a highly variable depth of coverage per library preparation. While imbalanced pools may account for some of the difference, library preparation methods had the biggest impact. Except for TruSeq, all the other library preparations start with shearing of the gDNA. For the other bisulfite-dependent protocols, the DNA fragments range between 200 and 400, whereas EMSeq allows for longer fragments (550 bp). TruSeq libraries tend to have short (130 bp) insert sizes and are therefore more suitable for 75bp paired-end read lengths. To overcome the impact of imbalanced sequence depth, this study provides robust recommendations for downsampling across sequencing types, showing both how different downsampling schemes (i.e., at the BAM level or at the methylation bedGraph level) are comparable, and how downsampled datasets can be directly compared to one another to assess the performance of the assays themselves.

The data provided herein (17) can guide the use of these DNA reference materials in epigenomics research, as well as provide best practices for experimental design in future studies. By leveraging seven human cell lines that are designated as publicly available reference materials, these data can be used as a baseline to advance epigenomics research.

EXAMPLE 3 RNAseq

The result of the ERCC consortium has found widespread use in the RNA sequencing community. The ERC consortium is a programme of NIST with the purpose of establishing external RNA control (ERC) and make these standards available to the public for quality control of RNAseq platforms (ERCC consortium: <https://www.nist.gov/programs-projects/external-rna-controls-consortium>). The consortium has developed a library of 96 external RNA spike-in control, which are distributed by NIST as Standard Reference Material 2374, with the focus on method validation (34). The RNA species are produced from cDNA clones, and are mixed in known ratios by the vendor. The idea is that ratios of mRNA transcripts between samples types can serve as indicator of biological differences, and thus controls and associated ratio performance metrics serve to understand reproducibility and validity of differential expression experiments. External spike-in control ratio measurements can serve as a truth set to benchmark the accuracy of endogenous transcript ratio measurements.

A library of 96 external RNA spike-in controls developed by the External RNA Controls Consortium (ERCC)¹ and distributed by NIST as Standard Reference Material 2374 can act as technology-independent controls for differential expression experiments. Method validation of differential expression experiments based on these ERCC controls is the focus of this work.

This set of ERCC was used in a RNAseq benchmarking study by the MAQC/SEQC consortium.

The EATRIS-Plus WP3 leader was involved in the development of RNA sequencing benchmarking studies, published in 2014 (6):

Technological advances have made deep RNA sequencing feasible, expanding our view of the transcriptome¹ and promising to permit quantitative profiling with large dynamic range (35). Recent comparisons of RNA-seq with established technologies for differential expression analysis have found good overall agreement between RNA-seq, qPCR and microarrays. In general, RNA-seq has provided increased detection sensitivity and opened new avenues of research in transcriptome analyses, such as the study of gene fusions, allele-specific expression and novel alternative transcripts. However, it has been shown that RNA-seq data exhibit measurement noise, which is a direct consequence of the random sampling process inherent to the assay. Assessments of RNA-seq have been limited to individual sequencing platforms and experiments, which may explain the variation of conclusions by study (36-39). Moreover, new platforms and protocols for RNA-seq have emerged in recent years. With the widespread adoption of RNA-seq, including the completion of large projects, such as ENCODE (40), TCGA (41) and ICGC (42), a comprehensive multi-site cross-platform analysis of RNA-seq performance is timely. Reproducibility across laboratories, in particular, is a crucial requirement for any new experimental method in research and clinical applications, and can only be tested in extensive comparisons of different sites and platforms. As in phase-I of the MicroArray Quality Control project (MAQC-I) (43), which tested agreement across sites and platforms for gene-expression microarrays, the FDA has coordinated the Sequencing Quality Control project (SEQC/MAQC-III), a large-scale community effort to assess the performance of RNA-seq across laboratories and to test different sequencing platforms and data analysis pipelines.

Figure 7

The SEQC (MAQC-III) project and experimental design. (a) Overview of projects. We report on a group of studies assessing different sequencing platforms in real-world use cases, including transcriptome annotation and other research applications, as well as clinical settings. This paper focuses on the results of a multicenter experiment with built-in ground truths. (b–d) Main study design. Similar to the MAQC-I benchmarks, we analyzed RNA samples A to D. Samples C and D were created by mixing the well-characterized samples A and B in 3:1 and 1:3 ratios, respectively. This allows tests for titration consistency (c) and the correct recovery of the known mixing ratios (d). Synthetic RNAs from ERCC were both added to samples A and B before mixing and also sequenced separately to assess dynamic range (samples E and F). Samples were distributed to independent sites for RNA-seq library construction and profiling by Illumina's HiSeq 2000 (three official + three unofficial sites) and Life Technologies' SOLiD 5500 (three official sites + one unofficial site). Unless mentioned otherwise, data show results from the three official sites (italics). In addition to the four replicate libraries each for samples A to D per site, for each platform, one vendor-prepared library A5...D5 was being sequenced at the official sites, giving a total of 120 libraries. At each site, every library has a unique bar-code sequence, and all libraries were pooled before sequencing, so each lane was sequencing the same material, allowing a study of lane-specific effects. To support a later assessment of gene models, we sequenced samples A and B by Roche 454 (3×, no replicates). (c) Schema illustrating tests for titration order consistency. Four examples are shown. The dashed lines represent the ideal mixture of samples A and B expected for samples D and C. (d) Schema illustrating a consistency test for recovering the expected sample mixing ratio. The yellow lines mark a 10% deviation from the expected response (black) for a perfect mixing ratio. Both tests (c) and (d) will reflect both systemic distortions (bias) and random variation (noise).

Figure 7 shows the overall study design. We sequenced commercially available reference RNA samples spiked with synthetic RNA from the External RNA Control Consortium (ERCC). Two distinct samples were assessed individually and also combined in known ratios. This allowed us to examine how well truths built into the study design, such as known relationships between samples within and across

sites, could be recovered from measurements. With no independent 'gold standard' feasible, these 'known truths' support an objective assessment of performance. To this end, we examined a multitude of properties, including complementary metrics of reproducibility, accuracy and information content. Such a multi-dimensional characterization is critical for the development of more powerful analyses of the underlying biological mechanisms in complex data sets because often there is a trade-off between one desirable property and another, such as accuracy versus precision. Analyses focusing on measurement quality metrics (8), spike-in controls and limits of detection (34) and the effects of analytic pipeline choice (44) are presented in separate studies.

The SEQC project also involved studies assessing RNA-seq in several research applications, including a performance analysis of neuroblastoma outcome prediction (45), a comparative investigation of toxicogenomic samples testing chemicals with different modes of action (46), and a comprehensive survey of tissue-specific gene expression in rat (47). In total, >100 billion reads (10 terabases) of RNA-seq data were produced and studied, which to our knowledge represents the largest effort to date to generate and analyze comprehensive reference data sets. A rigorous dissection of sources of noise and signal indicates that, given appropriate data treatment and analysis, RNA-seq can be highly reproducible, particularly in differential gene-expression analysis.

As shown in Figure 7, we used the well-characterized reference RNA samples A (Universal Human Reference RNA) and B (Human Brain Reference RNA) from the MAQC consortium (43), adding spike-ins of synthetic RNA from the External RNA Control Consortium (ERCC) (48). We then mixed A and B in known ratios, 3:1 and 1:3, to construct samples C and D, respectively. All samples were distributed to several independent sites for RNA-seq library construction and profiling by Illumina's HiSeq 2000 and Life Technologies' SOLiD 5500 instruments. In addition, vendors created their own cDNA libraries, which were distributed to each test site to examine 'site effects' independent of the library preparation process. To support an assessment of gene models, three sites also independently sequenced samples A and B using the Roche 454 GS FLX platform, providing longer reads. In total, for samples A to D, 108 libraries were sequenced on a HiSeq 2000, another 68 libraries on SOLiD, and 6 libraries on a Roche 454.

To compare technologies, we also examined expression profiles of the same reference samples generated from Affymetrix HGU133Plus2.0 microarrays in the MAQC-I study, and profiled and analysed these samples on several current microarray platforms (Methods). Besides RNA-seq and microarrays, we also considered qPCR-based protocols: we examined 843 TaqMan assays from the MAQC-I study, and in addition performed 20,801 PrimePCR reactions.

We next analyzed the reproducibility of detecting genes and junctions across measurement sites, platforms and analysis pipelines, as a key strength of RNA-seq is its inherent ability to identify splice sites *de novo*. To test this ability of RNA-seq to discover junctions, we first examined the HiSeq 2000 data because of the greater read length and depth. We considered three independent pipelines for *de novo* discovery of junctions independent of existing gene models: NCBI Magic (49), r-make (which uses STAR (50)) and Subread (51). All pipelines reported millions of junctions, with r-make predicting about 50% more than Subread and Magic, although almost all junctions found by Subread or Magic were also found by r-make. We also observed substantial but 12% lower agreement with TopHat2, regardless of whether it was run with or without gene model guided alignment (52) giving a total of 1,110,550 junctions consistently found by all five analysis variants. In total, 2.6 million previously unannotated splice junctions were called by at least one of the five analysis pipelines, yet only 820,727 (32%) were consistently predicted by all the methods, illustrating the considerable difficulty of reliably detecting splice junctions *de novo* with current analysis tools.

In this multi-site cross-platform study led by the US FDA, four well-characterized reference RNA sample mixtures with built-in truths were profiled to test RNA-seq reproducibility, accuracy and

information content in a detailed analysis of >30 billion reads on the reference samples alone. To our knowledge, the data presented here provide the deepest molecular characterization of any RNA samples to date.

We leveraged this deep data set to test the reliability and power of RNA-seq in exploring the complexity of the transcriptome. We studied the detection of known splice junctions and the discovery of unannotated junctions. *De novo* junction discovery was robust across sites both at low and at high sequencing depths, even beyond 10 billion aligned fragments. Many unannotated splice junctions were detected by multiple platforms and pipelines, with concordance directly reflecting the junction expression level. Similar to observations by ENCODE at the gene level (40), we observed three distinct classes of expression levels for splice junctions: highly expressed known junctions, known and unannotated junctions at medium levels, and many unannotated junctions found only at low expression levels. Although it has been proposed that an abundance of weakly expressed transcripts may reflect biological noise (53), the lower expression of these junctions may alternatively be the reason that they have so far received less attention in traditional experiments. With alternative transcript expression being dependent on cell type and experimental conditions, deep RNA-seq will continue to play a key role in fully exploring the transcriptomic repertoire, including the construction of extensive maps of alternative transcripts (36) highlighting splicing variants as well as alternative start and polyadenylation sites (40). *De novo* discovery constitutes a key strength of RNA-seq, and is reflected in the expansive transcriptional landscapes observed from different cells and tissues in the transcriptome re-annotation projects for human and rat (47) and the rich profiles collected in clinical and toxicogenomic applications in which many terabases of additional RNA-seq data were collected and analyzed (46, 54). Future studies can be conducted to identify novel alternative transcripts through full gene models, which allow the filtering of spurious junctions that cannot be explained by expression levels of alternative transcripts consistent with the distribution of reads that map to exons. discovery constitutes a key strength of RNA-seq, and is reflected in the expansive transcriptional landscapes observed from different cells and tissues in the transcriptome re-annotation projects for human and rat (47,56) and the rich profiles collected in clinical and toxicogenomic applications in which many terabases of additional RNA-seq data were collected and analyzed (46, 54).

Our read-mapping results underscore how crucial comprehensive gene model annotations are to accurate expression profiling (36). The human genome now has >55,000 well-validated genes, and the majority of them are not protein coding (40). Almost all human multi-exon genes exhibit alternative splicing, and spliced human genes have on average over nine alternative transcribed forms (40, 49). Additional genes and transcripts are still being discovered, even beyond the already expansive gene annotation from ENCODE (55). Notably, the NCBI AceView (49) database, which has >50,000 genes annotated from cDNA evidence, holds by far the largest and most-extensively validated set of splice junctions, with >300,000 well supported by the RNA-seq data reported in this study alone. Transcripts that may explain a particular phenotype may be missed by less-extensive annotations, stressing that the most comprehensive annotation for expression profiling is vital to accurate clinical research (46, 54). The characterization and, particularly, the quantification of alternative transcripts, however, still require further research. Although expression profiling of alternative transcripts is feasible, reattributing measurements to a set of alternative transcripts requires knowledge of all the alternative transcript forms of a gene, and involves combining information across the transcripts. For genome-scale RNA-seq, this is particularly difficult because of the sampling noise from low read counts for many transcripts, with recent work observing 300 million sequenced fragments to be required for the detection of a specific human alternative splicing event with 80% power (56).

This also highlights the value of targeted RNA-seq (57). Although simpler organisms such as *C. elegans* may be less affected by the difficulties of reliably attributing reads to alternative transcripts (58), analogous considerations will apply to research on mouse, rat and other complex transcriptomes. The need for longer-range information is a consequence of the fact that certain complex gene models cannot be resolved by the local information provided by either microarray probes or individual short

RNA-seq reads alone. Although read pairs of size-controlled fragments can improve on this, they also limit the recovery of shorter transcripts. Full alternative transcript profiling will thus greatly benefit from longer RNA-seq reads, which may eventually approach the full length of complex cDNAs. Combining deep RNA-seq for alternative transcript discovery with modern high-resolution microarrays for genome-scale quantification may provide an efficient approach for systematic transcript-level expression profiling (59).

Although none of the technologies we tested could provide reliable absolute quantification, relative expression measures agreed well across platforms, including RNA-seq, qPCR and microarrays. The majority of genes satisfied constraints based on the truths built into the study design. Going beyond earlier platform comparisons that considered individual performance metrics (36-39, 59-61), combined complementary metrics for a robust characterization of measurement performance that can be combined with further assays such as tests for strandedness, considerations based on the ERCC spike-in response, and tests for the exclusion of non-specific background. Notably, the important but difficult task of estimating and removing background noise, typically improves accuracy at the expense of precision.

Considering the substantial disagreements even between different types of qPCR-based assays, we conclude that there is no single 'gold standard.' Although our cross-platform comparisons reveal common trends, drastic systemic differences remain. Reference data sets such as the compendium presented here are invaluable for a systematic characterization of measurements, which is critical for reliable conclusions from large-scale experiments. Specifically, a closer examination of the varying amount of detected ERCCs per sample indicated substantial differences and inconsistencies even across libraries prepared from the same sample at the same site and sequenced by the same machine. This implies inherent limitations for the read out of absolute expression level estimates and absolute quantification (62). As the vendor-prepared libraries gave very uniform results across sites, the observed variations likely arose in library construction, and may partially be explained by platform-specific differences in kit chemistry and varying degrees of sample poly-adenylation (62). Therefore, in RNA-seq experiments, multiple libraries per examined condition or sample should be profiled.

We show that filters can improve robustness of differential expression calls and consistency across sites and platforms. For RNA-seq, removing small fold-changes as well as excluding low-expression measurements reduced the false discovery rate considerably and, in general, gave an improvement over microarrays (43) at similar sensitivity. These filters also achieved good inter-site agreement of lists of differentially expressed genes, with the performance of several (but not all) RNA-seq pipelines becoming comparable to that of microarrays. Even though a direct comparison of absolute expression levels across platforms was not possible, the filters yielded good agreement of differential expression calls between platforms, suggesting that differential expression analyses from different platforms could be combined.

Importantly, the observed sensitivity of results to pipeline choice suggests that substantial improvements in short-read RNA-seq analysis are still required, particularly for transcript identification and quantification. The data we collected in this multi-center study can serve as a benchmark set for further advances. Some recent progress can be directly attributable to the impact of more-successful read mappers (51, 54). In addition, although systematic and sample-specific variations in GC bias (63), sequence bias and non-specific signal can contribute to unwanted or missed differential expression calls, continued study of the confounding factors in RNA-seq can be expected to improve signal quality (36, 60, 63, 64), just as methodological developments have improved microarray signal read out, e.g. (65). Conversely, with several microarray designs tested here probing less than half of all known AceView genes, new microarray designs can take advantage of updated gene annotations and models refined by RNA-seq (59), as we have shown here with pilot microarrays.

Already today, RNA-seq can be used as a versatile tool for relative expression profiling, with comparable or superior performance to microarrays in many applications given sufficient read depth

and appropriate choice of analysis pipeline. An effective sequencing depth is clearly contingent on the experimental goals, with simple gene-level expression profiling only requiring 5–50 M single-ended reads for an appropriate analysis pipeline. A comprehensive characterization of alternative transcript expression benefits from the longer-range information of read pairs and requires considerably deeper sequencing. In our data set, at five million mapped fragments, >15,000 AceView genes could already be detected with strong support (16 reads), including ~10,000 RefSeq genes. Moreover, 10 million mapped fragments sufficed for differential expression analysis of the most strongly expressed genes in our study, reliably across sites. Other applications may require deeper sequencing, as is reflected by different metrics responding differently to an increase in reads for the samples and genes studied. Classifier performance, for instance, is directly related to the mutual information metric. Although 5 million mapped fragments easily gave a mutual information per gene comparable to that of HGU133Plus2.0 microarrays with MAS5, performance comparable to newer arrays and processing methods required about 50 million mapped fragments in this study, or even required considerably more, depending on the RNA-Seq analysis pipeline (*cf.* TopHat2+Cufflinks). In addition, the required read depth is also dependent on the genome size, transcriptional complexity (58), cellular distribution of stored versus active RNAs, biological noise (66) and the panoply of all other factors of cell biology and RNA dynamics. Our comprehensive multi-site cross-platform benchmark measurements under controlled settings thus complement and extend comparisons for individual biological experiments. In summary, the study and data collection presented here form an important milestone in the development and dissection of RNA-seq as a method for transcriptome profiling. The results based on data sets of this size and complexity and an array of independent measures as introduced by this study will contribute to a better understanding of the power and limitations of RNA-seq. This work is complemented by SEQC companion studies analyzing the application of RNA-seq to specific biological research and clinical questions (34, 44, 47, 54). The cumulative SEQC data sets with >100 billion reads (10 Tb) provide a key resource for testing future developments of RNA-seq, as required in clinical and regulatory settings.

EXAMPLE 4: proteomics

Mass spectrometry-based proteomics covers a wide range of applications. Untargeted approaches are used for protein identification, differential protein expression profiling between samples and analysis of post-translational modifications, whereas targeted approaches are designed for (absolute) quantitation of specific proteins or peptides in biological matrices. The diverse nature and rapid advances in both mass spectrometry technology and bioinformatics methods to analyse proteomics data poses significant challenges for the development of widely suitable reference material (67). There has been considerable international effort to develop appropriate quality control approaches, for example NIST offers reference materials such as yeast and human liver protein extracts (68, 69) or the NCI-7 cell line derived protein extract developed by CPTAC (70), and also commercially available standards are available (Sigma, Pierce), but currently there is no single strategy that is broadly applied in the field. Here, we will focus on untargeted proteomics experiments, as for targeted analyses often target-specific standards are used and pre-analytical and analytical methods are optimized for each target.

Proteomics experiments consist of different stages, which can affect reproducibility and reliability: (i) the pre-analytical stage, including protein extraction and proteolytic protein digestion (ii) the analytical stage consisting of LC-MS analysis with peptide separation by liquid chromatography and online mass spectrometric analysis (either data-dependent analysis (DDA) or data-independent

analysis(DIA)) and (iii) the post-analytical stage consisting of data processing and bioinformatic analysis.

Figure 8

A typical LC-MS experiment consists of sample preparation (pre-analytical stage), a liquid chromatography, a mass spectrometry, (analytical stage) and a bioinformatics stage (post-analytical stage). The sample preparation includes the proteolytic digestion of proteins into peptides. Next, consecutively the peptides are separated through liquid chromatography and measured through mass spectrometry. Finally, the acquired spectra are interpreted through bioinformatics means (figure from (67))

In a typical sample preparation for a proteomics experiment, several generic steps such as reduction, alkylation and proteolytic digestion can be recognized. However, sample preparation protocols are often optimized for specific sample types. To prevent a bias against laboratories specialized in other matrices than the provided reference materials (using sample preparation protocols that are not optimal for the reference material), variability caused by sample preparation can be excluded for quality assessment using commercial standards that have already undergone proteolytic digestion and are ready for LC-MS injection.

Besides sample preparation, technical performance of the LC-MS configuration is also an important factor that can cause variability. With a large range of different types of LC and MS instruments, calibration and tuning procedures are instrument and vendor specific and are usually checked and/or executed before each batch to limit technical variation. Besides calibration and tuning, quality control samples are used to monitor LC-MS batch-to-batch variation and variation within a batch, and finally blank runs are performed to assess sample carry-over.

For proteomics analyses, several commercial quality control samples are available. A quality control sample contains a mix of peptides (f.e. iRT standards), a single protein digest (f.e. BSA digest) or a whole cell lysate digest (f.e. HeLa cell line digest). Typically QC samples and blanks are used to monitor LC performance (retention time, peak width, peak shape, etc.) as well as MS performance (mass accuracy, fragmentation efficiency, signal intensity, etc.). The complexity of the QC samples that are used depends on the type of instrument and application, and most laboratories have developed their own system performance monitoring procedures.

Sample preparation and LC-MS analysis are often considered to cause most of the variability in proteomics experiments, but bioinformatic analysis can also contribute to variability to a large extent.

The mapping of peptides to a protein database can be performed using several different database search algorithms (f.e. Mascot, Sequest, PEAKS, MSFragger, MaxQuant, Spectronaut, etc.), each with a unique methodology and assumptions. Even when using a single database search engine, parameters need to be optimized to ensure optimal performance. Application of the data analysis workflow on the measured QC samples can be used to assess overall performance of the combined LC-MS and bioinformatic analysis, for example by plotting protein coverage (typically for single protein digests), or peptide spectrum matches and number of identified proteins (for complex QC samples).

The above mentioned quality control approaches are typically used to monitor variability of a proteomics workflow, but their focus is mainly on peptide and protein identification. Currently there are no reference samples or proficiency testing programs to monitor performance of label-free relative quantitation in differential protein expression profiling, which is currently one of the most used proteomic approaches. However, several benchmark studies have been published to monitor performance for differential protein expression profiling comparing different bioinformatic workflows or LC-MS configurations and/or methods (71-73). These studies all have a common experimental design, using a complex digests originating from different species (f.e. H. Sapiens, S. Cereviciae, E.Coli). The sample set that is analysed consists of mixes of these proteomes in different ratios, thereby providing a ground truth. This principle can be used as quality assessment to obtain insight in the performance of a system, but could also serve as a tool to investigate relative quantitative results but also peptide and protein identification in proficiency testing between different laboratories and analytical/post-analytical workflows.

We propose to develop a sample set for proficiency testing of label-free proteomic profiling using a similar setup as the benchmark studies mentioned above. To ensure broad applicability we will focus on the performance of the combined analytical and post-analytical stages by providing samples that already have been processed and are ready for LC-MS analysis. Also, the sample set should be useable for a wide range of instruments and analytical methods (both DDA and DIA). Therefore, we propose to generate a sample set of multiple samples consisting of mixes of tryptic digests from multiple species in different ratios, that can be used for proficiency testing. Participating laboratories can then analyse the samples using their optimised protocols for differential proteomics, without prior knowledge of the exact constitution of each sample to ensure unbiased analysis.

EXAMPLE 5: metabolomics

To ensure the success of a metabolomics experiment, researchers should follow several rules. The key is to obtain high-quality data with a minimum influence of technical bias emerging from the sample preparation and analytical assays themselves. The correct approach gives you the confidence that what you see in your data are biological differences and not an instrument “behaviour” during the data acquisition (74, 75).

The first step should be to ensure that your instrument set-up is working correctly. When it comes to metabolomics with the application of liquid chromatography (LC) separations coupled with mass spectrometry (MS) detection, a few general rules are recommended. Each mass spectrometry instrument vendor has available series of procedures to check the performance of the analytical platform. Usually, it applies direct injection of calibration mixture solution and evaluation by a control software with predefined performance tests. Failed calibration tests suggest that the instrument is not at its peak performance capacity, and we should not proceed with the experiment until the issues are solved. Evaluation of the liquid chromatography system should be performed in the same manner, although there are no or very few commercially available kits. One of the options is creating a quality assurance (QA) or system suitability sample, which will contain a mixture of known chemical standards. By running an analysis on these samples, we can evaluate the performance of the LC system and column by checking the behaviour of individual analytes (retention time with a tolerance of <2%, peak area deviation <10%, symmetrical peak shape, etc.), the system backpressure, stability of the column oven temperature and potential contaminants in the system. Having such a QA sample can monitor the system performance over time and potentially create a set of reference values. Unfortunately, such reference values are difficult to transfer across different laboratories because of the variety of LC systems on the market with multiple hardware configurations, and this fact is complicating the whole process. But having a set of in-house criteria built over time is highly recommended for each analytical assay.

The second step is to ensure that even if some technological bias appears, we can compensate for it (<https://epi.grants.cancer.gov/Consortia/mQACC/>). For this purpose, each experiment should contain (1) quality control, (2) quality assurance and (3) blank samples. Researchers should consider how the QC and QA samples will be used during their laboratory experiments and data processing in advance and prepare the samples accordingly. (1) QC samples prepared for intra-study assessment of data should have a representative composition of the biological material used in the experiment. Afterwards, the analytical accuracy, precision, and repeatability acquired from the QC sample data can be converted into metrics describing the quality of the data. One of the approaches is to create a pooled QC sample consisting of aliquots from every biological sample in the experiment. Such QC samples can be used for further data processing, e.g. peak-matrix filtering, especially in the untargeted metabolomics approach. Another way is to use a pooled sample from a studied population or a cohort (hundreds of samples) that is highly similar to the biological material in your experiment. (2) QC samples have their limitations when it comes to inter-laboratory comparison. To overcome this limitation is better to use standard reference materials (SRMs) commercially available (e.g. NIST SRM 1950). SRMs can be considered a great example of a comparable QA sample across different analytical platforms and laboratories. (3) To address the system background noise, extractables & leachables and sample preparation artefacts, it is essential to use blank samples. The preparation of blank samples should undergo the same procedures as other samples, except that biological material should be exchanged with suitable replacement (e.g. plasma for water). Based on the analysis of blank samples during data processing, we can subtract the background noise features, thus eliminating more of the analytical bias in the study.

Above all, we should highly stress the application of internal standards in each sample. Even if sometimes it is impossible to have an internal standard for every studied compound in the experiment,

carefully chosen standards compensate for bias introduced by wrong sample injection or liquid handling during the sample preparation procedures.

EXAMPLE 6: microRNA q-RT-PCR

Non-coding RNA including miRNAs are promising biomarkers in patient management. NGS and qRT-PCR are the most common techniques for their determination, both widely used in Health Care Systems. However, non-coding RNA implementation in clinical practice is still lacking consensus in several key aspects including normalization methods and reference values. These unsolved issues are important bottle necks for these biomarkers' contribution to Personalized Medicine.

In particular, for miRNAs determination by qRT-PCR reference values in healthy individuals have not been established yet. Since epigenetic mechanisms, to which miRNAs belong, are very specific for each individual, very large cohorts of healthy individuals, stratified by age, gender and human races should be analyzed for identifying robust reference values accurate for establishing pathological cut off of those biomarkers. Some approaches to this matter have been already published examining the relative plasma level stability of over 1000 different miRNAs across healthy subjects (Schlosser K et al., (2015). PLoS ONE 10(5): e0127443) and EATRIS-Plus multiomic approaches could contribute too.

Additionally, implementation of miRNAs in clinical practice also requires appropriate technical controls for assuring reproducibility and reliability of amplification values and proper normalization for correct data analysis. Technical controls include the addition and later amplification of exogenous added sequences, i.e. Spike ins (UniSp2, UniSp4 and UniSp5) and cel 39-3p, devoted to monitor RNA extraction and RT reaction. High variability in spike ins CTs strongly indicate unreliable performance. Standardized programs including NormFinder (<http://moma.dk/normfinder-software>) and GenNorm (<https://genorm.cmgg.be/>) are highly recommended for finding a trustful normalizer in different contexts. Moreover, technical controls and normalization are strictly required when serum and plasma samples are analyzed. Small amount of RNA and the absence of housekeeping microRNAs in blood samples force to tightly monitor qRT-PCR reproducibility. Similarly, , normalizers are also required in the case of tissue and cell samples. Classical small RNA reference controls exhibit stable expression levels in cells because of their fundamental "housekeeping" functions, but these RNAs are not routinely detectable in plasma. Therefore, housekeepers in blood samples have been defined from large data base including levels of miRNAs in blood samples. Indeed, some providers highly recommend a combination of miRNAs exhibiting consistent expression as potential housekeeping, including miR-191-5p, miR-103a-3p, let-7a-5p and miR-16-5p.

All these relevant approaches for miRNAs studies have been successfully and often used by our Lab at IRYCIS (76-78).

NEXT STEPS

Reference data and material will be made available to the community via the Multiomics Toolbox that EATRIS-Plus develops as part of Work Package 3.

ABBREVIATIONS

ABRF - Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities
ATCC - American Type Culture Collection (ATCC)
BS - bisulfite-only treatment
CPTAC - Clinical Proteomic Tumor Analysis Consortium
DDA - data-dependent analysis
DIA - data-independent analysis
EMSeq - enzymatic deamination
EpiQC - Epigenomics Quality Control
ERC - external RNA control
ERCC - External RNA Control Consortium
FDA – the Food and Drug Administration
GIAB - Genome-in-a-bottle consortium
IATA - The International Air Transport Association
IBBL - Integrated BioBank of Luxembourg
IRYCIS - Ramón y Cajal Health Research Institute
LC - liquid chromatography
LCLs - lymphoblastoid cell lines
LC-MS - Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry
MAQC - MicroArray and Sequencing Quality Control
MeDIP-seq - methylated DNA immunoprecipitation and sequencing
NCTR - National Center for Toxicological Research
NGS - next generation sequencing
OX - oxidative bisulfite treatment
PE - Performance Evaluation
PT - proficiency testing
QC - Quality control
RUMC - Radboud University Medical Centre,
SD - standard deviation (SD)
SERMAS - Servicio Madrilenio de Salud
SOP - Standard Operating Procedure
SOP - Standard Operating Procedure
TNBC - triple-negative breast cancer
UH - University of Helsinki
UP - Univerzita Palacky v Olomouci
UU - University of Uppsala
WES - whole-exome sequencing
WGBS - short-read whole-genome bisulfite sequencing

DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

Original due date of Deliverable 3.3 was 31/08/2021, extension was granted by the Project Officer until 31/03/2022.

ADJUSTMENTS MADE

n/a

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